

Principals' Supervisory Techniques and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the predictive influence of principals' supervision techniques on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. To guide the study, one objective, one research question, and one null hypothesis were formulated. The research adopted a predictive survey design. The population comprised 762 principals and 7,607 teachers across 254 public secondary schools in the state. A multistage sampling procedure involving purposive and stratified techniques produced a sample of 381 principals (50% of the population) and 1,481 teachers (30% of the population), giving a total of 1,862 respondents. Data were collected using two researcher-developed instruments: the Principals' Supervision Techniques Questionnaire (PSTQ) and the Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ). Face validation established content validity, while the Cronbach Alpha method yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81 for the independent variable and 0.90 for the dependent variable. Regression coefficients were employed to answer the research question, and simple linear regression was used to test the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that principals' supervision techniques significantly predicted teachers' job performance. Based on this result, it was recommended, among others, that principals should regularly conduct classroom visitations as a key supervisory strategy to identify teachers' challenges and provide necessary support, thereby enhancing job performance.

Introduction

Education is a vital tool for the development of any society. It ensures the acquisition of essential skills, knowledge, orientations, and values required for daily living and societal advancement. Thus, the level of development of any society is a reflection of the quality of its educational system. In Nigeria, there is a strong belief that higher educational attainment translates into improved living conditions and national development. Consequently, education has been adopted as an instrument for effecting national development (FRN, 2013).

Despite this, the nation continues to grapple with societal vices such as insurgency, moral decadence, drug abuse, human trafficking, and political as well as religious crises; many of which are linked to the poor quality of education. In some public secondary schools, the quality of education is so low that graduates often lack the skills necessary to overcome poverty, secure gainful employment, and contribute to societal growth.

With the introduction of free and compulsory education in Nigeria, public secondary schools have witnessed a sharp rise in student enrolment without a corresponding increase in teacher recruitment or infrastructural development. This mismatch has created serious challenges for school management and teachers' job performance. Inadequate classroom accommodation has forced some schools to convert staff rooms into classrooms, thereby depriving teachers of essential working space. This situation has hindered principals' ability to properly supervise teachers. In some cases, teachers attend school only to deliver lessons and leave immediately afterwards, leading to reduced commitment and poor performance. Similarly, inadequate infrastructure and an uncondusive learning environment adversely affect both teaching effectiveness and school management.

Furthermore, poor communication and bureaucratic bottlenecks have weakened collaboration between principals and teachers, reducing teachers' morale and limiting their contributions to school growth. Yet, the success or failure of any school system depends largely on the effectiveness of principals as managers, the quality of teachers, and their level of commitment. Achieving national educational goals rests heavily on the competences of principals and teachers.

As chief administrators, principals' management techniques play a crucial role in determining teachers' performance and commitment. Management techniques are systematic and analytical methods employed to improve decision-making, planning, efficiency, and control (Heine, 2010). They help boost morale, increase productivity, and foster teamwork by guiding employees toward organisational goals. Iwhiwhu (2010) noted that management techniques address all aspects of goal achievement, while Asiyai (2005) stressed that teacher performance involves the effective execution of instructional tasks that bring about desirable learning outcomes.

Teachers' performance encompasses classroom management, lesson preparation and delivery, student evaluation, introduction of innovations, use of instructional materials, and adherence to schemes of work. However, these tasks are often hindered by overcrowded classrooms, inadequate facilities, insufficient teachers, and dilapidated infrastructure. In many public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, classes of 80–100 students are common, far exceeding the 1:40 teacher–student ratio recommended by the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013). Such conditions negatively affect teachers'

morale, reduce cooperation with school authorities, and ultimately impair performance. Teachers' performance is typically evaluated based on two paradigms: the effectiveness paradigm, which focuses on student outcomes, and the teaching process paradigm, which emphasises teachers' and students' behaviours that are either inherently valuable or linked to learning outcomes (Strong et al., 2011). In Nigeria, poor student achievement is often attributed to poor teacher performance, which in turn is linked to weak management practices (Adegbesan, 2011; World Bank, 2018).

Principals' administrative competences, which range from supervision, communication, mentoring, decision-making, capacity building, and discipline to conflict management, are critical management techniques that influence teaching and learning. Among these, **supervision** stands out as a particularly important determinant of teachers' performance. Supervision involves overseeing the teaching–learning process to ensure that the school is effectively managed to achieve educational objectives. According to Kumar (2025), principals play a pivotal role in instructional improvement through effective supervision, which not only enhances teachers' competences but also ensures quality learning for students. In this way, supervision **may contribute** to sustaining a conducive teaching and learning environment, while also **potentially strengthening** the overall effectiveness of the school system.

Statement of the Problem

The day-to-day administration of secondary schools requires a high degree of managerial competency by principals and a good sense of commitment to work by teachers as those responsible for the interpretation and implementation of the school curriculum in the classroom setting. In Akwa Ibom State, the introduction of free and compulsory education has brought about a tremendous increase in students' enrolment without a corresponding increase in teachers' strength and provision of necessary infrastructures, which has posed a serious threat to management.

It has been observed in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State that teachers are assigned to teach overcrowded classes of over 100 students per class session due to enrolment increase as a result of the free and compulsory education scheme. This seems to pose a serious challenge to effective classroom management, lesson presentation and delivery. Some teachers seem not proficient in lesson content knowledge because they are assigned to teach those subjects that are outside their areas of specialisation, due to a shortage of manpower.

Many teachers tend to approach their job with resentment and prejudice because they are not allowed to contribute their ideas in school decision-making processes. Others tend to lack the requisite teaching skills due to absence of mentorship. Certain teachers exhibit some levels of mediocrity because they are not professional teachers but are employed as ad hoc staff under the guise of the “empower scheme” without acquisition of the requisite teaching qualification.

A close observation of the public secondary schools also reveals that many teachers teach with obsolete knowledge and archaic methods of teaching, without acquisition of the current computer skills necessary for the introduction of innovations into their teaching careers. This is due to a lack of opportunity to upgrade teachers through regular attendance in conferences, seminars and workshops for capacity-building purposes.

More often than not, teachers find it difficult to adhere to or complete their scheme of work due to frequent conflict escalation, which may take the form of student rampages, industrial action, strikes and pandemics, thereby disrupting academic calendars to the detriment of teachers' job performance. Many teachers tend to be involved in dereliction of duty, such as absenteeism, lateness to work, attrition, insubordination, negligence of duty and laxity without apparent reason, which are all detrimental to effective teaching performance and, to a reasonable extent, may be blamed on management incompetencies. This study therefore, investigates the predictive influence of principals' supervision techniques on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Research Question

To what extent do principals' supervision techniques predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypothesis

To guide the study, the research question was reformulated into this null hypothesis, tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

H₀: Principals' supervision techniques do not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Methodology

The study employed a predictive research design, considered appropriate because the main focus was to determine the extent to which principals' supervision techniques could predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools. This design allowed for the examination of existing variables without manipulation and provided the framework to assess the predictive influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

The study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, a South-South geopolitical zone popularly referred to as the Land of Promise. Created in 1987 with Uyo as its capital, the state has a population of over five million people and is bordered by Cross River State to the east, Rivers and Abia States to the west, and the Atlantic Ocean to the south. The people are predominantly Christians, with major occupations including farming,

fishing, trading, and weaving. English is widely spoken alongside several indigenous languages such as Ibibio, Annang, Ekid, Oro, and Obolo. Educationally, Akwa Ibom is notable for its many secondary schools, polytechnics, and universities, while administratively, it has 31 local government areas (LGAs) grouped into three senatorial districts (Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene). The state hosts 254 public secondary schools. The researcher's prior experience in the public school system provided both motivation and practical insights for choosing this study area.

The study population consisted of 762 principals and vice principals, alongside 7,607 teachers working in the 254 public secondary schools during the 2019/2020 academic session. From this population, a multistage sampling technique was applied. Stratification was first done by senatorial districts and local government areas, followed by proportional allocation and random selection of schools, principals, and teachers. In the final stage, purposive and stratified techniques were combined to ensure adequate representation across schools. This process yielded 381 principals, representing 50% of the total, and 1,481 teachers, representing 30%, giving a total sample size of 1,862 respondents. A reciprocal assessment approach was adopted in which each principal evaluated at least four teachers, and each teacher rated their principal, thereby ensuring a balanced 1:4 principal–teacher ratio and 4:1 teacher–principal ratio. A minimum of twelve teachers were sampled per school to enhance reliability.

Two instruments developed by the researcher were employed for data collection. The Principals' Supervision Techniques Questionnaire (PSTQ) contained 56 items covering seven supervisory dimensions with eight items each, while the Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) comprised 20 items assessing areas such as classroom management, lesson delivery, subject-matter knowledge, innovation, and student evaluation. Teachers responded to the PSTQ by rating their principals, while principals used the TJPQ to assess teachers. Both instruments were structured on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1). Items were derived from conceptual frameworks, empirical studies, and related literature.

Face validation of the instruments was conducted by experts in educational administration and measurement, who reviewed the items for clarity, relevance, and adequacy. The reliability of the instruments was established using the Cronbach Alpha method, yielding coefficients of 0.81 for the PSTQ and 0.90 for the TJPQ, which indicated strong internal consistency. For data analysis, regression coefficients were employed to address the research question, while simple linear regression analysis was applied to test the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. This enabled the study to determine the predictive power of principals' supervision techniques on teachers' job performance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question One:

To what extent do principals' supervision techniques predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?

The research question sought to find the extent to which principals' supervision techniques predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. In order to answer the research question, simple regression coefficient (R) was used and summary data shown in Table 3.1. :

Table 3.1: Extent to which principals' supervision techniques predict teachers' job performance

Variables	R	R ²	% Extent of prediction	Remark
Principals' Supervision Technique	.649	.421	42.1	low
Teachers' Job performance				

n = 1423

Source: Researcher field work, (2021).

Table 3.1 shows the extent to which principals' supervisory techniques predict teachers' job performance in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State. The value of R of .649 reveals that there exists a fairly positive relationship between principals' supervision technique and teachers' job performance. The coefficient of determination of .421 indicates that the principals' supervisory technique account for 42.1% of variation in teachers' job performance. The result therefore means that the supervisory technique of principals predicts teachers' job performance.

Hypothesis:

H₀: Principals' supervision techniques do not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Simple regression analysis was used to test the null hypothesis and summary data shown in table 3.2.

Table 3.2. Simple Regression of the Extent to which Principals' Supervision Techniques Predict Teachers' Job Performance

Variables	Source of Variables	SS	Df	MS	F-value	p-value	Decision
Principals' supervision Technique	Regression	282399.222	1	282399.223			
Teachers' job performance	Residual	389039.692	1421	273.777	1031.48	.000	Significant
	Total	671438.915	1422				

Significant P<.05Source: *Researcher field work (2021).*

The result in Table 3.2 reveals that the calculated F value was 1031.48 and the calculated p-value was .000, which was less than the p-significant value at .05 level of significance with 1422 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis, which stated that principals' supervision techniques do not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State,

was rejected. This implies that the extent to which principals' supervision techniques predict of teachers' job performance is significant.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that principals' supervision techniques significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the regression results indicated that supervision techniques accounted for 42.1% of the variation in teachers' job performance, a substantial proportion that underscores the importance of effective supervision in shaping educational outcomes. This implies that the quality of supervision exercised by principals is not merely related to teachers' performance but serves as a strong predictor of it.

In practical terms, the result reflects the reality that some principals in the state are not sufficiently committed to effective supervision. Many seldom remain in their offices long enough to monitor teachers' activities, thereby undermining the teaching and learning process. Where supervision is lax, teachers' productivity tends to decline, while consistent and structured supervision provides motivation and direction for improved performance. This outcome aligns with the assertion of Lawal (2003) that instructional supervision is essential for guiding teachers to effectively perform their duties and contribute maximally to the attainment of educational goals. Principals, as heads of schools, therefore serve as a key source of inspiration and accountability for teachers,

motivating them to strive for quality service delivery.

The result also corroborates Justine's (2008) view that organisations perform more effectively under leaders who demonstrate both people-oriented and task-oriented behaviours. Principals who balance concern for staff welfare with attention to instructional goals are more likely to foster high teacher productivity and cohesive school environments. Similarly, the findings are consistent with those of Iroegbu and Etudor-Eyo (2016), who established that teachers in schools where principals conducted adequate instructional supervision were significantly more effective than those in schools with insufficient supervision. Their study further emphasised that specific supervisory activities such as classroom observation, post-conference analyses, and follow-up strategies were instrumental in enhancing teaching effectiveness.

Taken together, the present findings suggest that supervision-conscious principals are able to provide direction, mobilise teachers towards shared goals, and instil a sense of orderliness in the school system. By predicting teachers' job performance significantly, supervision techniques emerge not simply as administrative routines but as strategic tools for achieving educational quality. This highlights the need for school leadership training programmes to prioritise supervisory competence, ensuring that principals are well-equipped to foster teacher effectiveness and improve student outcomes.

Conclusion

The study concluded that principals' supervision techniques significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The predictive strength of supervision underscores its role as a strategic determinant of teacher effectiveness and overall school performance. In other words, schools led by principals who adopt effective supervisory practices are more likely to record higher levels of teacher productivity and improved student learning outcomes.

Recommendation

In view of this, it is recommended that principals, as administrative and instructional leaders, should institutionalise systematic and routine classroom visitation as part of their supervisory duties. Such structured monitoring would not only provide firsthand insights into teachers' instructional challenges but also enable principals to offer timely feedback, guidance, and professional support. Furthermore, training programmes organised by the Ministry of Education and other stakeholders should emphasise supervisory competence, equipping principals with the skills needed to carry out effective supervision. A proactive and supervision-conscious leadership approach is likely to enhance teachers' job performance, strengthen instructional delivery, and ultimately contribute to the attainment of educational quality across public secondary schools in the state.

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